

Application of Python-Based Streamlit App for Evaluating Growth and Feed Efficiency in *Pterophyllum scalare*

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Abstract

This study investigates the Condition Index (CI) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) of Angel Fish (*Pterophyllum scalare*) cultured under two different feeding conditions over an eight-month rearing period. Two types of feed were utilized namely traditional fish feed and alternative feed incorporating Black Soldier Fly (BSF) larvae. This study assessed the impact of these diets on fish growth, health, and feed efficiency considering CI and FCR as proxies. Used a Python Streamlit app for calculations related to CI and FCR. The findings suggest significant differences in CI and FCR between the two groups, providing insights into sustainable and cost-effective aquaculture practices.

Keywords: Angel Fish, *Pterophyllum scalare*, Condition Index (CI), Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR), Black Soldier Fly (BSF).

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1. Introduction

In the sector of ornamental fish rearing, nutrition plays a pivotal role in fish growth, health, and economic viability. Condition Index (CI) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) are widely used parameters to assess fish well-being and feed efficiency. Insect-based feed for ornamental fishes is an innovative and sustainable alternative to traditional fish feeds. Rich in high-quality protein, essential amino acids, and lipids, these feeds promote vibrant coloration and enhance the immune system of ornamental fishes. Insects such as black soldier fly larvae, meal worms, and crickets are commonly used, providing a natural diet that closely resembles what fish consume in the wild. They are also more environmentally friendly, requiring less water and land for production than the conventional feed sources like fishmeal. Additionally, insect-based feeds reduce waste production and improve water quality in aquariums, making them an ideal choice for hobbyists and breeders.

Several researchers [1-29] have worked on different aspects of ornamental fish growth, distribution, trade, and their feed composition, but this study is the first initiative to use a Python Streamlit app for calculations related to CI and FCR of the ornamental fish.

The objective of this study is to evaluate CI and FCR in Angel Fish (*Pterophyllum scalare*) under two dietary regimes: a conventional fish feed and a diet incorporating Black Soldier Fly (BSF) larvae conducted during 2024 in two aquaria for a period of eight months (March to October). Thus, the study primarily aims to explore the potential of BSF-based feed as a sustainable alternative to conventional feed in ornamental fish culture.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Experimental Design

The study was conducted in a controlled aquarium environment for a period of eight months March 2024 to October 2024. Two separate aquariums (each with identical water quality conditions)

were maintained during the culture period. Fishes in aquarium A was fed with traditional feed, whereas fishes in aquarium B was fed with BSF larvae-based feed.

2.2 Data Collection

Fishes (n = 55) were monitored for growth parameters, including weight (W) and length (L), at regular intervals. The following parameters were calculated:

(a) Condition Index :

$$CI = \frac{W}{L^3} \times 100$$

Where CI is the average condition index, W is the average weight (g) and L is the average total length (cm) of the fish species. It is to be noted that the value of CI was generated as the output of a Python Streamlit app on analysing the Average Body Weight (ABW) and Average Body Length (ABL) of the selected ornamental fish species.

(b) Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) :

The FCR was calculated as per the expression

$$FCR = \text{Total feed intake} / \text{Total biomass gain.}$$

2.3 Fish Health and Wellness Tracker

The Fish Health and Wellness Tracker is a data-driven application developed using Python and Streamlit, designed to assess the health and efficiency of fish farming systems. The tool focuses on calculating two critical aquaculture performance indices: Condition Index (CI) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR), the outputs of which are displayed in Figures (1) and (2).

Figure 1: Fish Condition Calculator – Data Analysis with Streamlit.

The screenshot shows a web application titled "Fish Health & Wellness Tracker" with a logo featuring a fish and the letters "AM". The main heading is "FISH CONDITION CALCULATOR". On the left, there are four input fields: "Name of the fish species", "No. of fishes" (with a value of 1), "Weight of all fishes (in gm)", and "Length of all fishes (in cm)". Below these is a "Calculate CI" button. On the right, under the heading "Field Activities", there is a section titled "Condition Index" with a paragraph of text explaining the metric. Below the text is a small image of a woman in a red and yellow sari sitting on a red bucket, possibly handling fish.

Source: Authors.

Figure 2: FCR Calculator – Data Analysis with Streamlit.

The screenshot shows a web application titled "FEED CONVERSION RATIO CALCULATOR". On the left, there are six input fields: "Feed consumed in the initial day (in gm)", "Feed consumed in the final day (in gm)", "Number of days" (with a value of 1), "Biomass in the initial day (in gm)", "Biomass in the final day (in gm)", and "Number of days" (with a value of 1). Below these is a "Calculate FCR" button. On the right, under the heading "Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)", there is a paragraph of text explaining the metric. Below the text are two images: the top one shows a man in a brown shirt standing by a pond, and the bottom one shows a man in a blue patterned shirt standing next to a display board with fish illustrations.

Source: Authors.

Fig. 3. Fish Health Dashboard – Analysis & Communication via Streamlit.

Source: Authors.

2.4 Streamlit Framework

The application is built using Streamlit, allowing users to input fish data and calculate key aquaculture parameters *via* a simple web-based interface.

2.5 Session State Management

Various session state variables (`st.session_state`) store user inputs and calculation result to maintain continuity during interactions. In Streamlit, `st.session_state` is a way to store and retain user inputs, computed values, or any other variables throughout an interactive session. This means that when a user interacts with the app—such as entering data, adjusting sliders, or triggering calculations—the values are saved in `st.session_state`. This allows for continuity so that the app remembers previous inputs and results even when users navigate different parts of the interface or trigger re-runs of the script. Essentially, it helps maintain a seamless user experience by preserving data across interactions instead of resetting everything on each refresh.

2.6 Condition Index (CI) Calculation

CI is computed as a function of average weight and average length, using the formula:

$$CI = \left(\frac{\text{Average Weight}}{\text{Average Length}^3} \right) \times 100$$

2.7 Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) Calculation

The FCR metric assesses feed efficiency in fish, calculated as:

$$FCR = \frac{\text{Change in Feed Consumption}}{\text{Change in Biomass}}$$

where feed consumption and biomass changes are derived from user input.

2.8 User Interface & Input Handling

The UI includes multiple text inputs, number inputs, and buttons, ensuring an interactive user experience.

2.9 Data Visualization

The app dynamically displays results, including CI and FCR calculations, helping users quickly interpret data.

2.10 File Management & Deletion

Users can delete specific entries from the Excel file, ensuring data updates as needed.

2.11 Email Notification System

The app includes an email contact form that sends messages using SMTP, allowing communication with stakeholders Figure (3).

3. Results

3.1 Condition Index (CI) Analysis

Table 1: Length, Weight and CI of *Pterophyllum scalare* fed with BSF larvae

Months	Length (cm)	Weight (g)	CI
1	2.37	5.4	40.56
2	4.31	12.26	15.31
3	5.45	15.94	9.85
4	6.67	26.17	8.82
5	7.58	32.04	7.36
6	8.94	35.99	5.31
7	10.2	42.3	3.99
8	12.37	48.73	2.57

Source: Authors.

Table 2: Length, Weight and CI of *Pterophyllum scalare* fed with traditional feed

Months	Length (cm)	Weight (g)	CI
1	2.42	6.1	43.04
2	4.64	10.66	10.67
3	5.77	14.56	7.58
4	7.02	23.97	6.93
5	7.98	30.02	5.91
6	9.23	32.72	4.16
7	11.15	40.45	2.92
8	14.02	49.01	1.78

Source: Authors.

The average CI values indicated that fish fed with BSF larvae exhibited a higher CI value (Table 1) compared to those fed with traditional feed (Table 2). This suggests a better physiological condition and nutritional uptake in fish fed with BSF larvae.

3.2 Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) Evaluation

A lower FCR was observed in fish consuming BSF larvae-based feed (1.22), compared to the fish fed with traditional feed (1.88) indicating higher feed efficiency. The improved FCR suggests that BSF larvae provide better digestibility and nutrient assimilation.

4. Discussions

Among aquarium fishes, angel fish (*Pterophyllum scalare*) is a good old and most preferred fish by aquarium hobbyists and a lot of studies have been reported on various aspects including its nutrition, biology and growth [30-38].

The present study aims to analyse these indices considering *Pterophyllum scalare* as candidate species to understand their growth patterns and optimize feeding protocols for ornamental fish sector in fresh water environment, although saline water has considerable impact on estuarine organisms [39-45]. In this study, CI values of fish in the BSF-based feed group were consistently higher than those in the traditional feed group. This suggests that fish fed with BSF larvae exhibited better growth and overall health. The improved CI could be attributed to the superior nutrient profile of BSF larvae, which provide essential amino acids, lipids, and minerals required for optimal physiological development. The FCR results revealed a significant difference between the two feeding groups. Fishes in the BSF-based feed group recorded an average FCR of 1.22, while those in the traditional feed group had an FCR of 1.88. The lower FCR observed in the BSF-fed fishes indicates a higher efficiency in feed utilization, which can be linked to improved digestibility and better nutrient assimilation. The superior FCR in the BSF-based diet aligns with findings from previous studies suggesting that insect-based protein sources enhance nutrient retention and growth performance in fish. The high protein and lipid content of BSF larvae likely played a crucial role in improving metabolic efficiency, thereby reducing feed wastage, and enhancing biomass accumulation. The use of BSF larvae in aquaculture offers multiple advantages

beyond improved feed efficiency. From an economic perspective, BSF larvae production is cost-effective, utilizing organic waste as feed, thus reducing dependency on expensive fishmeal. Environmentally, the incorporation of BSF larvae contributes to sustainable waste management by recycling organic materials into valuable protein sources, mitigating the ecological footprint of aquafeed production.

Despite the promising results, challenges remain in scaling up BSF larvae-based feed for commercial aquaculture. Factors such as feed formulation optimization, consumer acceptance, and regulatory approvals need to be addressed. Further research should explore the long-term effects of BSF-based diets on different fish species and their impact on product quality in terms of taste, texture, and nutritional composition.

5. Conclusions

The present study primarily utilizes a Python Streamlit app developed by Ranajit Samanta of RCC Institute of Information Technology, West Bengal (India) for calculations related to Condition Index (CI) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR). The study demonstrates that feeding *Pterophyllum scalare* with BSF larvae-based feed improves both CI and FCR, making it a promising sustainable alternative to traditional fish feed. Further research is recommended to assess long-term impacts on fish health, coloration, and reproductive performance.

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